

Employers' Feedback on Teacher Education Program Graduates, Batch 2024 of Nueva Ecija University of Science and Technology, Gabaldon Campus

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Abstract: This study explored employers' feedback on the competencies and work performance of the 2024 graduates of the Teacher Education Program at Nueva Ecija University of Science and Technology (NEUST), Gabaldon Campus. Utilizing a quantitative research design, the study gathered data through structured survey questionnaires distributed via Google Forms to 10 employers. The research focused on assessing graduates' competencies in professional development, moral values, research and problem-solving, community extension, technology integration, and overall work performance. Findings revealed that most NEUST graduates demonstrate strong ethical behavior, commitment to lifelong learning, and effective work habits. Employers strongly agreed that the graduates possessed desirable competencies, particularly in areas of moral values and professional conduct. While graduates were positively evaluated across all areas, some areas, such as creativity in using educational technology and gathering/analyzing feedback, were identified as needing improvement. The study concludes that NEUST has successfully produced capable and ethically grounded teacher education graduates, though enhancements in technology integration and experiential learning are recommended. These insights are valuable for educational institutions, policymakers, and future educators in aligning teacher training with the dynamic needs of the educational landscape.

Keywords: *Teacher Education Graduates, Employer Evaluation, Employability Skills, Professional Development, Work Performance.*

Introduction

Higher education institutions are meant to produce quality and competitive graduates for the job market and nation-building. It produces a quality workforce for the social, economic, and cultural advancement of the country. However, graduates' chances of a teaching position are extremely low, or they have work not match their school and training. But if they can pass the board examination, they can more easily be placed in jobs related to their specialization, and they can obtain a job sooner. In this way, they may contribute to the labor participation rate and employment rate of the country. Employability has received deep interest in colleges. In recent years, many people have re-evaluated teacher preparation programs in light of modifications to the education program. The quality of teacher education programs is a significant determinant of the effectiveness of future educators in the field. As graduates from these programs enter the workforce, their performance is often evaluated not only by their academic accomplishments but also by employer feedback. These evaluations offer critical insights into the strengths and weaknesses of teacher education curricula and help in aligning educational institutions' goals with the demands of the teaching profession. Teacher education plays a crucial role in preparing future educators to meet the challenges of the ever-evolving educational landscape. Evaluating the performance of teacher education graduates is essential in assessing the effectiveness of the curriculum and its alignment with the needs of the workforce. One significant way to measure this is through employer feedback, which provides valuable insights into how well these graduates are equipped to thrive in their professional roles (Cochran-Smith et al., 2018).

The employer's feedback for the 2024 batch of teacher education graduates in Nueva Ecija University of Science and Technology (Gabaldon Campus) will become particularly relevant, as these graduates faced unique challenges due to the COVID-19 pandemic. The shift to online learning and the rapid adaptation required of both educators and students have likely impacted the skill sets of these new teachers (Trust & Whalen, 2020). The Batch 2024 graduates of NEUST Gabaldon faced unique challenges, having undergone part of their education during the COVID-19 pandemic. The shift to online learning required these future educators to adapt quickly to new teaching methods and technologies (Trust & Whalen, 2020). Understanding how well these graduates are performing in the field, as perceived by their employers, is essential in assessing how effectively the NEUST Gabaldon Campus teacher education program has prepared them for the modern classroom. Therefore, exploring employers' perspectives on this batch of graduates can provide insights into how well teacher education programs have adapted to these new realities and what further changes might be necessary. By gathering feedback from employers, it can greatly help graduates of education courses determine if they are ready to become good and effective teachers. Teachers can help develop a school to achieve high-quality education. In pursuit of its commitment towards sustainable development (Pentang, 2021), the Western Philippines University - College of Education (WPU-CED) is strongly engaged in developing quality teacher education graduates ready for local

and global employment. Bok (2017) emphasized that colleges and universities must restructure programs to better prepare aspiring professors for teaching.

Even though this study is more specialized to the teacher education graduates, insights from employers hiring people with degrees not related to their field of employment will provide useful comparative data. Such a wider perspective may make employers more aware of the transferable skills and general qualities that will prepare graduates from teacher education programs for success, regardless of their previous educational background. Feedback from employers on their experience with teacher education graduates must form the central basis for determining the effectiveness of these programs. Beyond the teaching profession, however, is an enormously diverse array of professional types that are neither directly educational nor associated with distinct sets of expectations and demands.

As future Educators of the Nueva Ecija University of Science and Technology (NEUST) Gabaldon Campus, assessing the feedback of employers regarding the performance of its teacher education graduates from Batch 2024 is particularly important. This feedback not only reflects the overall quality of training these graduates received but also highlights areas for improvement in the curriculum to better meet the demands of the educational sector. According to Darling-Hammond (2017), employer feedback is a critical tool for understanding how teacher education programs contribute to the readiness of teachers to work in diverse educational settings.

This study aims to determine the feedback employers provide regarding students who have graduated from the teacher education program at Nueva Ecija University of Science and Technology (Gabaldon Campus). The feedback from employers provides a valuable perspective on the readiness of teacher education graduates to meet the challenge of modern classrooms. It also offers insights into the graduates' competencies in key areas such as content knowledge, classroom management, communication, and adaptability (Cochran-Smith et al., 2018). Understanding how employers perceive the graduates' performance can inform improvements in teacher education programs and ensure that graduates are better equipped to succeed in diverse educational settings.

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework of the research serves as the overall framework of this entire research.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

Figure 1 shows the research Conceptual Framework of the study of the employer's feedback towards the graduate's learned competency in terms of Professional Development, Moral Values, Research and Problem-Solving, Community Extension Programs, and Technology in Education, as well as in Work Performance. All of this shows the visual

representation of how employers' feedback can be leveraged to enhance educational programs, ensuring that graduates are better prepared for the workforce. By addressing the specific competencies valued by employers, educational institutions can refine their curricula and training methods, which are used to enhance the preparation of future graduates.

Statement of the Problem

While numerous studies have examined the experiences and perceptions of teacher education graduates, a critical gap remains in understanding how employers perceive their preparedness and effectiveness in real-world educational contexts. This study aims to address this gap by systematically examining employer feedback, particularly in relation to how well teacher education programs align with the actual needs of schools and learners. Specifically, this research seeks to describe the respondents' profiles in terms of age, sex, civil status, and length of service. It also aims to determine the nature of the respondents' work, whether in teaching or non-teaching positions. Furthermore, the study investigates the extent to which the competencies acquired by teacher education graduates are relevant to their current job requirements, particularly in the areas of professional development, moral values, research and problem-solving skills, community extension programs, and technology in education. Finally, the study evaluates the effectiveness of teacher education graduates based on their work performance as assessed by their employers.

Methodology

Research Design

The quantitative research design was used in this study; the focus is on a measurable number of people that can be statistically useful. Using a Google form, researchers collected information on current jobs and the employment environment. This quantitative research is used in order to quantify the problem by generating numerical data that can be transformed into usable statistics. The researchers were conducting a descriptive study in which numerical data were collected from participants via a Google Form. This method enabled targeted data collection, accurate analysis, inexpensive research, and the ability to replicate the study. This design aims to leverage statistical insights into the determinants of employment-related outcomes.

Respondents of the Study

The respondents of the study are the employers of teacher education program graduates' batch 2024 from Nueva Ecija University of Science and Technology-Gabalton Campus. The respondents in the study were 10 employers from various institutions and industries who provided feedback on the performance and competencies of teacher education graduates. These included representatives from the Local Government Unit of Dingalan (LGU), Wheeltek Gabaldon, Pharma Otso Gabaldon, Gabaldon Essential Academy, Inc., Sutherland in Palayan City, St. Patrick's Academy, Inc., Palawan Group of Companies, Dingalan Central School, Foundever in Manila City, and Desk-up in Cabanatuan City. The inclusion of employers from both public and private sectors, as well as educational and non-educational organizations, ensured a diverse and comprehensive perspective on the relevance and effectiveness of the graduates in various professional settings.

Sampling Technique

This study employed purposive sampling to select the respondents. Specifically, the participants were chosen based on a predefined criterion: they must be employers of teacher education graduates. This technique was deemed appropriate as it allowed the researchers to intentionally select individuals who possess direct knowledge and relevant experience in evaluating the competencies, preparedness, and work performance of the graduates in actual workplace settings. By focusing on employers from both educational and non-educational institutions, the study ensured that the data collected were rich, context-specific, and aligned with the objectives of assessing the relevance and effectiveness of teacher education programs.

Research Instrument

The researcher used a structured survey questionnaire to collect information from the selected respondents. The questionnaire was designed in two parts. The first part consisted of the respondents' socio-demographic profile, and the second part consisted of questions based on the set objectives. The questionnaire was a closed-ended one, in which respondents were only allowed to choose an answer from the given scale by filling in and ticking the space provided that corresponded to their answer. The response scale used a Likert scale (a commonly used measurement scale),

specifically the 4-point scale. Likert scales are a structured way for researchers to gather diverse opinions and attitudes. They allow respondents to express agreement, disagreement, or neutrality concerning statements or questions.

Validity of Research Instrument

The questionnaire design for the study underwent validation for face and content validity. The research instrument was reviewed for face validity by content and field experts, including the researcher adviser, research instructor, research statistician, Chair of Teacher Education Program, the Panel Members, and the English Critic. This group of experts checked the information as expected according to the research topic. Views on the content and structure would be incorporated in the final draft of the instrument. This was established to ensure the content validity of the research instrument, ensuring it solicited the right information before it is endorsed to the English critic and research practitioners from the Teacher Education Program. This group of experts carefully reviewed the questions to assess the appropriateness and adequacy of the instruments.

Data Collection

As agreed, the researchers used Google Forms to collect the necessary information. Before commencing data collection, the researchers would submit a formal letter request to the Office of Teacher Education Program Chairperson seeking approval to conduct this research. Once approval is granted, we will proceed to the Registrar's Office to obtain a comprehensive list of all Teacher Education graduates for 2024. Subsequently, we would contact one student from each course to inquire whether an active group chat exists that includes all members. If this method proves insufficient, we would trace them individually, providing each graduate with a link to the Google Form containing the survey questionnaire. Google Forms is a versatile online survey tool that makes it easy to create, distribute, and analyze surveys. Respondents would be given sufficient time to complete the questionnaire to ensure thoughtful and accurate responses. Upon completion, the survey results would be tallied and tabulated for analysis.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The collected data were analyzed using quantitative and descriptive statistical approaches. Descriptive statistics, in the analysis of data, descriptive statistics such as frequency, percentage, and mean were employed to summarize and interpret the responses. Furthermore, this study used a four-point Likert scale to measure respondents' level of agreement with each instrument item. Each scale point corresponds to a specific range and verbal interpretation: a rating of 4 (3.51–4.00) denotes Strongly Agree, indicating a high level of agreement; a rating of 3 (2.51–3.50) signifies Agree, reflecting a moderate level of agreement; a rating of 2 (1.51–2.50) represents Disagree, indicating a low level of agreement; and a rating of 1 (1.00–1.50) corresponds to Strongly Disagree, reflecting a very low level of agreement. This scaling framework ensures a clear, systematic, and consistent interpretation of respondents' perceptions across all measured variables.

Ethics in Research

Researchers have a fundamental duty to protect the rights of their participants. According to Colnerud (2015), ethical considerations help prevent or reduce harm to human participants during primary data collection. Thus, protecting human rights is very important in all research. Each respondent should feel empowered to decide whether they want to take part in the study, ensuring that participation is entirely voluntary. It's essential to create a respectful environment by avoiding any offensive or unacceptable language when presenting questionnaires. This respect is vital for fostering trust and openness.

Central to ethical research practices is the principle of informed consent. Researchers must provide sufficient information and assurances to allow individuals to understand what participation entails. This means that participants should be able to make a fully informed, considered, and freely given decision, free from any pressure or coercion.

The language used in questionnaires must be carefully considered to avoid any offensive, discriminatory, or otherwise unacceptable terms. This thoughtful approach not only respects the dignity of each respondent but also enhances the quality of the data collected.

Additionally, safeguarding respondents' privacy is of paramount importance. Researchers must ensure that responses are kept confidential and that there is no risk of plagiarism or misuse of answers. Participants' identities should be protected, and they should have the option to remain anonymous if they wish.

In summary, ethical considerations in research are crucial for protecting participants' rights, ensuring voluntary and informed participation, and maintaining their privacy and dignity throughout the process. By adhering to these principles, researchers can foster a responsible and respectful research environment. (Cilliers and Viljoen, 2021). In the current trend of research, it is illegal to violate human rights in the context of research.

Results

Profile of the Respondents

Table 1 presents the demographic profile of the respondents, including age, sex, civil status, length of service, and nature of work. In terms of age, the data reveal that 3 respondents (30%) were within the 20–30 age group, while the majority, comprising 5 respondents (50%), were aged 30–40 years. The remaining 2 respondents (20%) were aged 40 years and above. This distribution indicates that most respondents are in the early to mid-career stage, suggesting they have sufficient professional experience to assess graduates' competencies. Regarding sex, the results show that the majority of respondents were female (6, 60%), while male respondents comprised 4 (40%). This indicates a relatively balanced representation, although females slightly outnumbered males in the sample.

Regarding civil status, 6 respondents (60%) were single, while 4 (40%) were married. The predominance of single respondents may be associated with the sample's age distribution, as many fall into age groups where marriage may not yet be prioritized. Supporting this observation, data from the Philippine Statistics Authority indicate that the typical age at first marriage in the Philippines ranges from 27 to 29 years. Regarding length of service, the majority of employer-respondents (6, 60%) have been in service for 1 year or more, while 2 respondents (20%) have been employed for 1 to 6 months, and another 2 respondents (20%) for 7 to 12 months. The prevalence of respondents with longer tenure is methodologically advantageous, as it suggests that these employers have had sufficient time to observe and evaluate the sustained work performance of NEUST graduates. Consequently, their feedback is likely to be more comprehensive, experience-based, and reliable.

Finally, regarding the nature of work, the findings indicate that 3 respondents (30%) supervise graduates in teaching positions, whereas the majority, 7 respondents (70%), employ graduates in non-teaching roles. This distribution suggests that a significant proportion of NEUST teacher education graduates from Batch 2024 are employed outside the formal teaching sector. This trend aligns with broader patterns in Philippine higher education, where graduates of teacher education programs pursue diverse career paths, including roles in business process outsourcing, local government, and private enterprises. This highlights the importance of assessing graduate competencies not only in pedagogical skills but also in transferable competencies applicable across various professional contexts.

Table 1.

Profile of the Respondents.

Age	Frequency	Percentage
20 - 30 years old	3	30
30 - 40 years old	5	50
40 years old or above	2	20
Total	10	100%
Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Male	4	40
Female	6	60
Total	10	100%
Civil Status	Frequency	Percentage
Single	6	60
Married	4	40
Divorced	0	0
Widowed	0	0
Total:	10	100%
Length of Service	Frequency	Percentage
(1-6 Months)	2	20
(7-12 Months)	2	20
1 Year and above	6	60
Total	10	100%
Nature of Work	Frequency	Percentage
Teaching Positions	3	30
Non-Teaching Positions	7	70
Total	10	100%

Employers' Feedback on Employees' Professional Development

Table 6 shows that NEUST teacher education graduates from Batch 2024 are perceived as strong professional learners, with an overall mean of 3.75, interpreted as Strongly Agree. The highest-rated indicators, each with a mean of 3.82, include consistently seeking opportunities for professional growth, sharing learning and insights with colleagues, demonstrating commitment to continuous improvement, and engaging in reflective practice. In contrast, the indicator on active participation in training programs and professional learning communities obtained the lowest mean of 3.47, although still interpreted as Agree.

Table 2.

Employers' Feedback on Professional Development

Professional Development	Weighted Mean	Verbal Description
1. NEUST graduates consistently seek opportunities for growth and learning in their field.	3.82	Strongly Agree
2. NEUST graduates participate actively in training programs and professional learning communities.	3.47	Agree
3. NEUST graduates apply new skills and knowledge from professional development to their work.	3.76	Strongly Agree
4. NEUST graduates take initiative to stay current with the latest trends and best practices in their profession.	3.76	Strongly Agree
5. NEUST graduates share insights gained from professional development with colleagues.	3.82	Strongly Agree
6. NEUST graduates set professional development goals and take concrete steps to achieve them.	3.76	Strongly Agree
7. NEUST graduates demonstrate a commitment to continuous improvement in their performance.	3.82	Strongly Agree
8. NEUST graduates reflect on their professional practice for improvement.	3.82	Strongly Agree
9. NEUST graduates seek feedback and incorporate it into their ongoing professional growth.	3.76	Strongly Agree
10. NEUST graduates contribute to the professional development of others through mentoring or teaching.	3.76	Strongly Agree
Overall mean	3.75	Strongly Agree

Employers' Feedback on Moral Values

Table 3 indicates that employers perceive NEUST teacher education graduates as demonstrating strong moral values, with an overall mean of 3.79, interpreted as Strongly Agree. Among the indicators, the highest-rated items, each with a mean of 3.82, include demonstrating workplace integrity, maintaining confidentiality, managing conflicts effectively, and prioritizing the well-being of others. Meanwhile, the lowest-rated indicator is empathy toward diverse groups, which obtained a mean of 3.71, although still interpreted as Strongly Agree.

Table 3.

Employers' Feedback on Moral Values

Moral Values	Weighted Mean	Verbal Description
1. NEUST graduates demonstrate honesty and transparency in all professional interactions.	3.81	Strongly Agree
2. NEUST graduates consistently adhere to ethical guidelines and professional standards.	3.76	Strongly Agree
3. NEUST graduates show respect for the dignity and rights of others in the workplace	3.82	Strongly Agree
4. NEUST graduates maintain confidentiality and trust in handling sensitive information.	3.82	Strongly Agree
5. NEUST graduates handle conflicts or disagreements with fairness and integrity.	3.82	Strongly Agree

Table 3 (continued)

6. NEUST graduates demonstrate responsibility in decision-making, considering the impact on others.	3.76	Strongly Agree
7. NEUST graduates encourage ethical behavior among others by setting a positive example.	3.76	Strongly Agree
8. NEUST graduates show empathy and understanding in working with diverse groups of people.	3.71	Strongly Agree
9. NEUST graduates consistently promote fairness and equity in their professional actions.	3.82	Strongly Agree
10. NEUST graduates make decisions that prioritize the well-being and safety of others.	3.82	Strongly Agree
Overall mean	3.79	Strongly Agree

Employers' Feedback on Research and Problem-Solving

Table 4 shows that NEUST teacher education graduates demonstrate strong research and problem-solving competencies, with an overall mean of 3.70, interpreted as Strongly Agree. The highest-rated indicator, with a mean of 3.76, is the ability to critically evaluate multiple perspectives before making decisions. Most of the remaining indicators yielded closely clustered mean scores of 3.71, indicating consistently high ratings across analytical and collaborative problem-solving skills. On the other hand, the indicators on data gathering and evaluation and integrating feedback from others obtained the lowest means of 3.65, although both are still interpreted as Strongly Agree.

Table 4.

Employers' Feedback on Research and Problem-Solving

Research and Problem Solving	Weighted Mean	Verbal Description
1. NEUST graduates use critical thinking to analyze problems thoroughly before proposing solutions.	3.71	Strongly Agree
2. NEUST graduates gather and evaluate relevant data before making decisions.	3.65	Strongly Agree
3. NEUST graduates develop innovative solutions to address complex problems.	3.71	Strongly Agree
4. NEUST graduates collaborate with others to analyze problems and find effective solutions.	3.71	Strongly Agree
5. NEUST graduates critically evaluate different perspectives before making decisions.	3.76	Strongly Agree
6. NEUST graduates apply research-based strategies to solve problems effectively.	3.71	Strongly Agree
7. NEUST graduates anticipate potential challenges and develop proactive solutions.	3.71	Strongly Agree
8. NEUST graduates adjust their approach based on new data or changing circumstances.	3.71	Strongly Agree
9. NEUST graduates identify the root cause of issues and work to address them.	3.71	Strongly Agree
10. NEUST graduates integrate feedback from others to refine problem-solving approaches.	3.65	Strongly Agree
Overall mean	3.70	Strongly Agree

Community Extension Program

Table 5 indicates that NEUST teacher education graduates demonstrate strong competencies in community extension, with an overall mean of 3.65, interpreted as Strongly Agree. The highest-rated indicator, with a mean of 3.76, is the ability to use community feedback to adjust and improve programs. Other indicators, including building local

partnerships, demonstrating cultural awareness, and linking educational programs to community needs, each obtained a mean of 3.71, reflecting consistently high ratings. Meanwhile, the indicators on designing community-based programs addressing local issues (3.53) and evaluating program impact (3.59) received comparatively lower mean scores, although both remain within the Strongly Agree range.

Table 5.*Community Extension Program*

Community Extension Program	Weighted Mean	Verbal Description
1. NEUST graduates actively participate in community extension programs that benefit the broader community.	3.59	Strongly Agree
2. NEUST graduates build strong partnerships with local organizations to enhance program outcomes.	3.71	Strongly Agree
3. NEUST graduates design community-based programs that address pressing local issues.	3.53	Strongly Agree
4. NEUST graduates take leadership roles in community extension projects, inspiring and motivating others to participate.	3.65	Strongly Agree
5. NEUST graduates evaluate the impact of community extension programs and identify areas for improvement.	3.59	Strongly Agree
6. NEUST graduates demonstrate cultural awareness when planning and implementing community programs.	3.71	Strongly Agree
7. NEUST graduates foster a sense of social responsibility by engaging others in community service.	3.65	Strongly Agree
8. NEUST graduates help to connect educational programs with community needs and resources.	3.71	Strongly Agree
9. NEUST graduates communicate the goal and outcomes of community programs clearly to stakeholders.	3.65	Strongly Agree
10. NEUST graduates use feedback from the community to adjust and improve programs.	3.76	Strongly Agree
Overall mean	3.65	Strongly Agree

Technology in Education

Table 6 shows that NEUST teacher education graduates demonstrate strong competencies in technology integration, with an overall mean of 3.74, interpreted as Strongly Agree. The highest-rated indicator, with a mean of 4.00, is the utilization of online resources to supplement classroom instruction. Several indicators also received high ratings of 3.80, including staying updated with emerging technologies, engaging in collaborative digital activities, participating in continuous professional development in educational technology, and involvement in technology-based projects. In contrast, the indicator on creativity and innovation in using technology to address instructional challenges obtained the lowest mean of 3.40, interpreted as Agree.

Table 6.*Technology in Education.*

Technology in Education	Weighted Mean	Verbal Description
1. NEUST graduates integrate technology effectively into teaching and learning activities.	3.60	Strongly Agree
2. NEUST graduates stay up to date with new educational technologies and incorporate them into their work.	3.80	Strongly Agree
3. NEUST graduates utilize online resources to supplement classroom instruction and enhance learning.	4.00	Strongly Agree
4. NEUST graduates demonstrate creativity and innovation in using technology to solve instructional challenges.	3.40	Agree
5. NEUST graduates collaborate with colleagues through digital platforms.	3.80	Strongly Agree

Table 6 (Continued)

6. NEUST graduates receive continuous professional development related to educational technology.	3.80	Strongly Agree
7. NEUST graduates participate in the evaluation and selection of new educational technologies.	3.80	Strongly Agree
8. NEUST graduates participate in collaborative projects that involve technology, such as creating digital content or using online learning platforms.	3.80	Strongly Agree
9. NEUST graduates use technology to create interactive and engaging learning experiences.	3.60	Strongly Agree
10. NEUST graduates use technology to create interactive and engaging learning experiences.	3.80	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean	3.74	Strongly Agree

Work Performance

Table 7 indicates that employers perceive NEUST teacher education graduates as demonstrating high levels of work performance, with an overall mean of 3.76, interpreted as Strongly Agree. The highest-rated indicators, each with a mean of 3.82, include receiving and following clear instructions, asking clarifying questions when necessary, and understanding the broader impact of their work. Several indicators also obtained consistently high mean scores of 3.76, including adequacy of training, adherence to quality standards, time management, compliance with standard operating procedures, and the ability to suggest improvements in the workplace. Meanwhile, the indicator on continuous learning as a means of improving work quality received the lowest mean of 3.65, although it still falls within the Strongly Agree category.

Table 7.

Work Performance

Work Performance	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Rating
1. NEUST graduates receive clear and detailed instructions on how to complete tasks.	3.82	Strongly Agree
2. NEUST graduates are equipped with adequate training to meet the quality standards.	3.76	Strongly Agree
3. NEUST graduates demonstrate a consistent understanding of the expected quality benchmarks.	3.76	Strongly Agree
4. NEUST graduates ask questions if they do not understand the instructions.	3.82	Strongly Agree
5. NEUST graduates effectively manage their time to complete tasks on schedule.	3.76	Strongly Agree
6. NEUST graduates follow the standard operating procedures of the company and/or institution.	3.76	Strongly Agree
7. NEUST graduates are engaged in continuous learning to enhance their quality of work.	3.65	Strongly Agree
8. NEUST graduates are empowered to suggest improvements to quality- related processes.	3.76	Strongly Agree
9. NEUST graduates assess the quality of their work before submission.	3.71	Strongly Agree
10. NEUST graduates understand the impact of their work on the overall quality of the product and/or service.	3.82	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean	3.76	Strongly Agree

Discussion

The findings indicate that NEUST teacher education graduates exhibit strong professional learning behaviors, particularly in areas that promote both individual and collective development. Specifically, the high ratings on reflective practice, continuous improvement, and knowledge sharing suggest that the institution has effectively fostered a culture of lifelong learning among its graduates. Moreover, the ability of graduates to extend their learning to colleagues

highlights the development of collaborative and leadership-oriented competencies expected of teacher education completers.

Nevertheless, the relatively lower rating on participation in training programs and professional learning communities may suggest the presence of external or structural constraints, such as limited access to professional development opportunities or insufficient institutional support in the workplace. Importantly, this finding does not necessarily reflect a lack of motivation among graduates but rather points to contextual limitations that may hinder their engagement in formal learning environments. Consequently, teacher education institutions may consider strengthening pre-service exposure to professional learning communities, particularly through practicum-based experiences that simulate or integrate collaborative professional development structures. These results are consistent with the findings of Darling-Hammond et al. (2017), who emphasized that effective professional development is characterized by sustained engagement, collaboration, and alignment with practice. Thus, the alignment of these characteristics with the competencies demonstrated by NEUST graduates suggests that the curriculum effectively prepares students for continuous professional growth in diverse educational contexts.

Similarly, the findings suggest that moral and ethical competence is a defining strength of NEUST teacher education graduates. The consistently high ratings across indicators such as integrity, confidentiality, and conflict management reflect graduates' preparedness to meet the ethical demands of professional environments. Indeed, these competencies are essential in teaching and other professional settings, where ethical decision-making and interpersonal responsibility are critical.

Despite these positive outcomes, the relatively lower rating on empathy toward diverse groups, although still within the *Strongly Agree* range, highlights an area for potential enhancement. In the context of increasingly diverse and multicultural educational and workplace environments in the Philippines, this finding suggests that while graduates possess strong foundational ethical principles, there may be a need to further strengthen their relational and cultural responsiveness. Therefore, integrating more explicit and context-sensitive approaches to multicultural education within the curriculum may help address this gap and enhance graduates' ability to engage effectively with diverse populations. These results are consistent with the arguments of Sanger and Osguthorpe (2019), who emphasized that moral development in teacher education must be both intentional and contextually grounded. In this regard, graduates should not only be guided by ethical standards but also be equipped to apply these principles effectively across varied and complex professional settings.

In terms of research and problem-solving competencies, the findings indicate that NEUST graduates possess strong analytical and critical thinking skills, particularly in their ability to critically assess multiple perspectives prior to decision-making. This suggests that graduates are equipped with higher-order thinking abilities that enable them to make informed and reflective decisions, which are essential in instructional planning and classroom management. Furthermore, the consistently high ratings across most indicators demonstrate that the teacher education program effectively develops both individual and collaborative problem-solving abilities.

However, the relatively lower ratings in data gathering and evaluation, as well as in integrating feedback from others, point to areas that may require further strengthening. These findings imply that while graduates possess a solid theoretical foundation in research and analysis, their practical application of evidence-based practices—such as systematically collecting data and utilizing feedback for improvement—may still be developing. This gap may be attributed to limited opportunities for applied research and data-driven reflection during pre-service training. Accordingly, there is a need to enhance the integration of action research and experiential learning components within the curriculum to better prepare graduates for evidence-based professional practice. Supporting this interpretation, Schleicher (2018) emphasized that educators who are capable of synthesizing data and implementing evidence-based strategies are more effective in improving student outcomes. Hence, strengthening this dimension within the NEUST teacher education program is essential for further enhancing graduate competencies.

Moreover, the findings suggest that NEUST graduates exhibit commendable competencies in community extension, particularly in their responsiveness to community needs and their ability to engage collaboratively with stakeholders. Notably, the highest rating on the use of community feedback highlights a strong orientation toward reflective and adaptive practice, indicating that graduates view extension work as a dynamic and iterative process rather than a one-time service activity. Likewise, the strong ratings on partnership-building, cultural awareness, and alignment of programs with community needs demonstrate graduates' capacity to function as effective linkages between academic institutions and the communities they serve.

On the other hand, the relatively lower ratings on designing community-based programs and evaluating program impact point to limitations in the technical and strategic aspects of community extension. These results suggest that while graduates are proficient in implementing and participating in established programs, they may be less confident in independently conceptualizing, designing, and assessing new initiatives. This gap may be attributed to limited exposure

to community-based project development and evaluation methodologies during pre-service training. In support of this interpretation, Corpuz, Time, and Afalla (2022) reported that teacher education graduates in the Philippines generally demonstrate strong participation and cultural sensitivity in extension activities but require more structured and sustained training in program design and impact evaluation. Therefore, strengthening these components within the curriculum may further enhance graduates' effectiveness in community engagement and development initiatives.

Furthermore, the findings indicate that technology integration is a significant strength among NEUST graduates. The perfect rating on the use of online resources highlights their strong capability to incorporate digital tools in enhancing instructional delivery. This result is particularly relevant in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic, which necessitated a rapid transition to online and hybrid learning modalities. Consequently, the ability of graduates to effectively adapt and utilize technology reflects the resilience and technological preparedness fostered by the NEUST teacher education program.

Additionally, the consistently high ratings across indicators related to technological awareness, collaboration, and professional development suggest that graduates perceive technology as an essential component of their professional practice rather than merely a supplementary tool. This demonstrates a positive orientation toward continuous learning and adaptation in an increasingly digital educational landscape.

Nevertheless, the comparatively lower rating in creativity and innovation when using technology points to a gap between technical proficiency and pedagogical innovation. While graduates are competent in utilizing existing digital tools, they may be less confident in designing innovative, technology-driven solutions to instructional challenges. This distinction is critical, as effective technology integration extends beyond usage to include creative and context-sensitive application. Supporting this interpretation, Tondeur et al. (2017) emphasized that structured instructional modeling, hands-on experiences, and reflective pedagogical inquiry during teacher education are essential in fostering innovative uses of technology in teaching. Therefore, enhancing these components within the curriculum may further strengthen graduates' capacity for creative and transformative technology integration.

Finally, the findings suggest that NEUST graduates possess strong work performance competencies that align well with employer expectations across various professional settings. The highest-rated indicators reflect graduates' ability to follow instructions effectively, communicate for clarification when needed, and recognize the broader implications of their responsibilities within the organization. Collectively, these characteristics indicate not only task efficiency but also professional accountability and organizational awareness, which are essential qualities in both teaching and non-teaching professions.

Moreover, the consistently high ratings across indicators related to training adequacy, quality standards, time management, and workplace procedures demonstrate that NEUST graduates are well-prepared to adapt to professional environments and meet organizational expectations. Their ability to suggest workplace improvements also reflects initiative and engagement, suggesting that graduates are capable of contributing positively to institutional development.

However, the comparatively lower rating on continuous learning may indicate challenges in sustaining self-directed professional growth within demanding workplace environments. Although graduates are perceived as competent learners, differences in workplace support systems and opportunities for professional development may influence their capacity for ongoing improvement. This finding highlights the importance of strengthening reflective practice, lifelong learning habits, and self-directed professional development during pre-service education. These findings support the study of Padilla and Ladores (2019), who found that teacher education institutions emphasizing practicum experiences, assessment literacy, and reflective practice tend to produce graduates who are more proactive in enhancing work quality and adapting to workplace demands. Consequently, further strengthening these components within the NEUST teacher education curriculum may contribute to even higher levels of graduate performance and professional growth.

Conclusion

The findings of the study reveal that NEUST teacher education graduates possess strong professional and ethical competencies as perceived by their employers. The consistently high ratings in areas such as professional development, honesty, respect, integrity, and commitment to continuous learning indicate that the institution effectively cultivates ethical values and a lifelong learning mindset among its graduates. These qualities demonstrate the graduates' readiness to meet the professional and moral demands of diverse workplace environments.

Furthermore, the results show that graduates demonstrate commendable competencies in research, problem-solving, and technology integration, reflecting their preparedness to adapt to contemporary educational and professional challenges. However, comparatively lower ratings in areas such as integrating feedback, data gathering, and creativity in educational technology suggest the need for further enhancement of applied and experiential skills. These findings

imply that while graduates possess strong theoretical foundations, additional emphasis on practical application and innovation may further strengthen their professional capabilities.

Moreover, the study highlights the positive contributions of NEUST graduates in both community engagement and workplace performance. Employers recognized graduates for their responsiveness to community needs, collaborative abilities, and adherence to workplace standards and responsibilities. Nevertheless, areas such as designing community-based initiatives and sustaining continuous professional improvement indicate opportunities for further institutional support and curriculum enhancement. Overall, the findings affirm that the NEUST teacher education program effectively prepares graduates for professional practice while also identifying specific areas for continuous improvement to ensure greater responsiveness to evolving educational and workplace demands.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, several recommendations are proposed. First, the results of this study may serve as a baseline for enhancing experiential learning opportunities within the Teacher Education Program. The university may further strengthen the practical competencies of its graduates by incorporating more hands-on and immersive learning strategies, such as simulated research activities, collaborative data analysis exercises, and feedback integration tasks. These approaches may help improve graduates' adaptability, critical thinking, and workplace problem-solving skills.

Second, the study may serve as a basis for strengthening technological and innovation-oriented training within the curriculum. Greater emphasis may be placed on the integration of digital tools, creativity-driven platforms, and innovative instructional design to better prepare graduates for modern and technology-driven educational environments. Such initiatives may further enhance graduates' confidence and competence in applying technology creatively and effectively in professional practice.

Third, the findings may guide the university in expanding community engagement initiatives and professional learning networks. Encouraging and supporting student participation in community extension programs and professional learning communities may reinforce civic responsibility, collaborative engagement, and continuous professional growth. Strengthening these opportunities may also enhance graduates' ability to respond effectively to community needs and workplace demands.

Finally, the data gathered in this study may serve as a valuable reference for understanding employers' feedback regarding the Teacher Education Program graduates, Batch 2024, of the Nueva Ecija University of Science and Technology – Gabaldon Campus. The findings may also provide useful baseline information and empirical support for future researchers who intend to conduct related studies on graduate competencies, employability, and employer satisfaction.

Author Contributions

Both authors contributed equally to the completion of the study. One author primarily managed the supervision, validation, and manuscript review processes, while the other took the lead in data collection, data analysis, and manuscript preparation.

Conflict of Interest Statement

The author declares no competing interests.

AI Use Declaration

This study utilized Grammarly to review and correct grammatical errors in the manuscript.

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